

TILAK JO'RA SHE'RIYATINING O'ZIGA XOSLIGI

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada iste'dodli o'zbek shoiri Tilak Jo'ra ijodining o'ziga xosligi to'g'risida so'z borgan.

Kalit so'zlar: she'riyat, mavzu, Tilak Jo'ra ijodi, mavzu, badiiy mahorat, poetik ifoda.

Tilak Jo'ra o'zbek she'riyatining o'ziga xos uslub va badiiy mahoratga ega ijodkorlaridan biridir. Shoir ijodi betakror poetik ifoda va ramzlarga boy. Uning she'rlarida aks etgan ramzlar qatida tuyg'u va fikr uyg'unlashgan, teran falsafa va ibratli o'git mujassamlashgan. Yorqin tasvirlarda aks ettirilgan badiiy manzarada milliy ruh yaqqol seziladi.

Shoirning lirik qahramoni Vatanning tabiati, go'zal manzarasidan mutaassir bo'ladi. Uning ko'rk-u tarovatini o'zgacha bir muhabbat bilan madh etadi. Ayni paytda ona tabiat, jonajon yurtning ajib tarovati shoirning lirik qahramoni qalbida g'aroyib kechinmalarni paydo qiladi, uning hissiy va aqliy olamida qo'zg'olon paydo qiladi. Dilgir tuyg'ular og'ushida isyonkor ruh g'alayon qiladi. Satrlar ortida shoirning dardli, o'rtangan qalbi bo'y ko'rsatib turadi. Bu dard erk dardi, hurriyatga, zulm va zo'ravonlikdan xoli bo'lgan mukammal hayotga, haqiqatga, ezgulikka intilgan ozod ruhning nidolari bo'lib jaranglaydi.

Tilak Jo'raning lirik qahramoni tabiatga nazar tashlay turib unda o'zini ko'rgandek bo'ladi, undan ibrat olib, fikrga toladi, uning ajib tarovatidan ilhom olar ekan, go'yo uning tinib-tinchimas ruhi orom olgandek bo'ladi. Lirik kechinmalarida yurt va uning ertasi uchun o'z-o'ziga katta mas'uliyat bilan qaraydigan insoning badiiy olami jo bo'lganligiga guvoh bo'lish mumkin. Shoirning:

Sening uchun Vatanim

Bir tup terak ekmadim!.. [1.44]

satrlarida Vatan kelajagi uchun mas'ul insoning armoni ifoda etilgan.

Shoir yurtining tabiatidan hayratlangan qalbidan qoniqmaydi, undan yanada kattaroq, bundan-da kuchliroq mutaassirlikni talab etadi.

Bu bog'lar ko'rkiga yayrab boqmasam,

Bir soyday kuymanib, kuylab oqmasam,

Chaman deb, chaman-chun o'zni yoqmasam,

Atirgul tikanin sanching ko'zimga! [1.47]

Shoirning satrlaridan el-yurtga fidoyilikni o'ziga mas'uliyat va burch deb bilgan vatanparvar insonning ma'naviy olami namoyon bo'ladi. To'g'ri, vatanparvarlik tuyg'usi ifoda etilgan she'rlar ko'pligini e'tirof etish mumkin. Ammo bu she'rda shoirning badiiy mahoratini yaqqol ko'rsatib turadigan yana bir qator jihatlar mavjud. Bunda ijodkor vatanga oshuftalikni uning tabiatidagi go'zalliklarga bog'lab talqin etadi. Uning ko'rki-tarovatini chinakamiga his etmaslik, uni chinakamiga sevmaslik jazoga loyiqligi haqidagi hukmni o'ziga so'rab oladi.

Shoirning lirik qahramoni ruh erkinligi, insonlarning ozod va farovon hayot kechirishini chinakamiga istaydi. Shu boisdan ham shoirning satrlarida namoyon bo'lgan lirik qahramon ruhiyati aksariyat holatlarda bezovta, kuyunchak, sertashvish holatda namoyon bo'ladi. Masalan, "Ruhiyat" she'rini olaylik. Unda qalbini ochgan lirik men ruhi so'nib qolgan, bag'ri dimiqqan, qalbida ohlar, tog'day og'ir dog'lar bor. Ammo imkonsizlikdan qo'llar bog'liq, umid esa dilda jon saqlamoqda. Natijada u qalbini ochib to'yib-to'yib baqirishni istaydi. Ammo bu ham shoirga armondur:

Bu qanday zamon, oxir!
To'yib-to'yib baqirmoq,
Yonib-yonib chaqirmoq
Endi bir armon desang. [1.5]

Shoirning "Sanduvoch erding, bo'lding andalib" deb boshlanuvchi she'rda ham erkka intilgan lirik qahramonning kechinmalari qushga murojaat shaklida ifoda etiladi.

Shoirning badiiy mahoratini namoyon qiluvchi jihatlar bir qancha bo'lib, eng muhimlaridan biri tabiat va inson kechinmalarining uyg'unlikda tasvirlanishi bilan xarakterlanadi. "Bizni doim o'rab turgan tabiat va hayot voqealarini poetik ifoda qilib inson tasavvurini boyitish va uning ongiga ta'sir o'tkazish adabiyotning asosiy vazifasidir" [3.338]. Badiiy ijoddagi bu vazifa kitobxonning tasavvurlarini boyitishi barobarida uning poetik idrok ko'lamini ham kengaytirishga xizmat qiladi. O'quvchi tabiat go'zalliklarini teran his etish imkoniyatiga ega bo'lishi bilan bir qatorda hodisalar mohiyatida yotgan hayot sirini, ilohiy mo'jizalar haqiqatini anglashga intila boradi. Natijada esa adabiyot orqali kishilarning hayot maktabidan ibrat olish, xulosa chiqarish ko'nikmalari orta boradi. Masalan, "U bir qushcha edi, mittigina jon" she'rda shoirni oddiygina bir qushchaga nisbatan qilingan nohaqlik og'rintiradi. She'rda tasvirlangan goh u shoxda, goh bu shoxda tabiatdan zavq olib, xirmonlar sha'niga kuylab uchib yurgan beozor qushchani birov ermak uchun bir o'q bilan xalok etadi.

Hech kim unga tutmadi aza,
Hech kim bunga qilmadi parvo.

Qush zoti-ku ko‘p erur, ammo
O‘sha erkin,

o‘sha hur qushcha

Endi yo‘qdir yorug‘ dunyoda. [1.44]

She’rda ijodkor badiiy adabiyotda qadimdan talqin etib kelingan ezgulik va yovuzlik kurashi talqinini yana bir, kichik bo‘lsa-da, ta’sirli voqea haqidagi hikoyasi bilan to‘ldiradi.

Shoirning she’rlarida ezgulikka ishonch, kelajaaka teran nigoh bilan qarash sezilib turadi. U tabiat haqida so‘z yuritadimi yoxud inson va jamiyatning murakkab masalalariga e’tibor qaratadimi, she’rlarining mazmun-mohiyatiga yorug‘ kunlarga umidvorlik tuyg‘usini singdirib boradi. Boychechakdan oldin,

Turnalardan oldin,

Bahorni qarshilab,

Paxsa devor ostidan

chiqar chumoli,

Yuzlariga sepkil toshgan qizday

Hovlimning yuziga

toshar chumoli,

Chumolidan ham oldin

Bahorni qarshilab,

Yuragimda g‘ivirlar –

Ko‘zlarimda ochilgan –

boychechaklar... [1.53]

Ko‘rinib turibdiki, shoir tabiat va inson kechinmalarini parallellikda tasvirlash orqali teran fikr ifoda etmoqda. Boychechaklar ezgulikka umidvor lirik qahramon tuyg‘ularini poetik jihatdan ifoda etishga xizmat qilmoqda. Ushbu satrlar insonning qalbida go‘zallikka, ezgulikka oshuftalikdek nozik tuyg‘ularning hamisha mujassam bo‘lishi, uning kechinmalari tabiat bilan uyg‘unlikda ekanligi bilan bog‘liq tasavvurlarimizni boyitadi.

Umuman olganda, Tilak Jo‘ra o‘zbek she’riyati xazinasini sermazmun va g‘oyaviy-badiiy jihatdan betakror ijod namunalari bilan boyitishga xizmat qildi. Shoirning asarlari yurt tarovati, inson qalbining nozik kechinmalari, ona tabiatning jozibasi o‘ziga xos tarzda tasvir etildi. Shoirning asarlari kitobxonning qalbida ezgulikka muhabbat tuyg‘usini oshirishga xizmat qilib kelmoqda.

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